

Synthesis, crystal structure and magnetic properties of tetranuclear dysprosium(III) cluster

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Abstract : Single-molecular magnets (SMMs) formed from metal-organic complexes are very promising candidates for information storage devices. A new tetranuclear cubane like Dy^{III} coordination compound, [Dy₄(L)₆(μ₃-OH)₄(μ₂-OH)(H₂O)₄]Cl·7H₂O (complex 1) has been synthesized by using Schiff base ligand 2-{(2-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-methylidene}amino}benzoic acid (L) and characterized by single crystal X-ray crystallography. Magnetic studies reveal that complex 1 exhibits single-molecule magnet (SMM) behavior at temperature lower than 1.8 K.

Keywords : Dysprosium cluster, Schiff base ligand, crystal structure, single-molecule magnet.

Introduction

Single-molecule magnets (SMMs) are individual molecules that can function as nanoscale magnets below a blocking temperature with potential applications in high density information storage, quantum computing and MRI contrast agents^{1,2}. These molecules can be magnetized in a magnetic field and retain the magnetization when it is switched off and significantly show hysteresis loops reminiscent of magnets³. Since the discovery of first SMM [Mn₁₂O₁₂(OAc)₁₆(H₂O)₄]^{4,5}, many compounds have been reported on SMM by several groups particularly concentrated on 3d-metal ions^{6,7}. In recent years, researchers have been focused on the design and synthesis of new single-molecule magnets by using 4f-metal ions⁸⁻¹⁵ which shows fascinating magnetic behavior, high spin and also magnetic anisotropy. Ln^{III} ions, such as Dy^{III} is ideal for the synthesis of SMMs due to their large uniaxial isotropy and high spin¹⁶⁻¹⁸. The presence of unquenched orbital momentum causes the anisotropy in Dy^{III} and the anisotropy can be modified by ligand field¹⁹. Compounds with Dy^{III} ion can exhibit various topologies such as linear, tri-

angular, planar, cubane, pyramid, wheel, disc and a trigonal prism^{8,10,15,20-24}.

In this work, we report the synthesis, crystal structure and magnetic properties of new Dy₄ cubane compound, [Dy₄(L)₆(μ₃-OH)₄(μ₂-OH)(H₂O)₄]Cl·7H₂O (complex 1) (L=2-{(2-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-methylidene}amino}benzoic acid, Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Schiff base ligand.

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without any further purification. *o*-Vanillin, anthranilic acid, *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis (2-hydroxy ethyl)-ethylenediamine and DyCl₃·6H₂O were obtained from

Sigma-Aldrich and ethanol, methanol and dichloromethane were purchased from Merck.

Preparation of Schiff base ligand :

The Schiff base ligand, 2-{{[2-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)methylidene]amino}benzoic acid, was synthesized according to the procedure reported²⁵ by Fan *et al.* 6.6 g of *o*-vanillin, 6.0 g of anthranilic acid and 85.0 ml ethanol were taken in round bottom flask reaction mixture was stirred at 40–60 °C for 1.5 h. Red precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried in vacuum. Yield : 10.1 g (86% based on anthranilic acid) and purity was higher than 98%.

Preparation of complex 1 :

56.0 mg Schiff base ligand, 2-{{[2-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-methylidene]amino}benzoic acid (0.2 mmol) and 0.2 ml *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis (2-hydroxy ethyl)ethylenediamine (0.2 mmol) in 10 ml methanol were stirred for 45 min at room temperature. 75.0 mg DyCl₃·6H₂O (0.2 mmol) was added to the above mixture, and the reaction mixture was stirred again for 1 h. Finally 6.0 ml of dichloromethane was added. The solution was then filtered and the filtrate left undisturbed at room temperature. Red crystals, suitable for single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis were obtained after one week. Yield : 13.0 mg (23% based on ligand). Elemental analysis (%) Calcd. for C₉₀H₆₆ClDy₄N₆O₄₀ : C, 40.55, H, 2.47, N, 3.15; Found : C, 37.44, H, 4.19, N, 3.30; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3468 (m), 1635 (s), 1385 (m), 671 (w), 601 (w), 541 (w), 458 (w), 432 (w), 406 (m).

Characterization methods :

The infrared spectrum was measured on a Perkin-Elmer “Spectrum two FT-IR” system by using KBr pellet preparation method, Elemental analysis was performed on “Thermo scientific FLASH-2000” elemental analyzer and Thermogravimetry Analysis (TGA) was performed using “Melter Toledo TGA/DSC-1” apparatus in a temperature range between 25

and 800 °C under N₂ with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹.

The single crystal data for complex **1** was measured on a CCD Agilent Technologies (Oxford Diffraction) SUPER NOVA diffractometer by using graphite-monochromated MoK_α radiation (λ_{α} = 0.71073 Å). The structure was solved by direct methods using SHELXS-97²⁶ and refined by full matrix least-squares with SHELXL-97, refining on F^2 . The positions of all the atoms were obtained by direct methods. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Crystallographic data, collection and refinement details related to complex **1** are summarized in Table 1 and selected bond lengths and angles are given in Table 2 and Table 3.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements of complex **1** were obtained on a finely ground polycrystalline

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement of complex **1**

	Complex 1
Formula	C ₉₀ H ₆₆ ClDy ₄ N ₆ O ₄₀
Formula weight	2556.95 g/mol
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P 1 21/n 1 (14)
<i>a</i> (Å)	18.0965(11)
<i>b</i> (Å)	15.1210(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	36.8631(17)
β (°)	103.96(0)
<i>U</i> (Å ³)	9789.06(1220)
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>T</i> (K)	293
<i>F</i> (000)	5200
$\rho_{\text{Calcd.}}$ (mg m ⁻³)	1.81
μ (MoK _α) (mm ⁻¹)	17.860
Data measured	56373
Unique data	18929
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.212
2 θ_{max} (°)	74.3194
w <i>R</i> ₂ (all data)	0.449
<i>S</i> (all data)	1.244
<i>R</i> ₁ [<i>I</i> ≥ 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	
Goodness of fit F^2	1.264

Table 2. Selected bond angles (°) for the Dy₄ aggregate

Bond distances (Å)					
Dy1-O1	2.321(13)	Dy1-O3	2.307(14)	Dy1-O7	2.378(15)
Dy1-O5	2.324(14)	Dy1-O666	2.367(14)	Dy1-O444	2.380(13)
Dy1-O111	2.347(13)	Dy1-O114	2.355(14)	Dy2-O9	2.362(14)
Dy2-O11	2.290(14)	Dy2-O6	2.445(16)	Dy2-O555	2.745(16)
Dy2-O444	2.354(13)	Dy2-O111	2.347(13)	Dy2-O333	2.322(14)
Dy2-O777	2.402(15)	Dy3-O15	2.302(15)	Dy3-O13	2.394(15)
Dy3-O17	2.414(16)	Dy3-O114	2.354(13)	Dy3-O333	2.353(13)
Dy3-O111	2.366(14)	Dy3-O555	2.433(14)	Dy3-O999	2.372(14)
Dy4-O19	2.473(15)	Dy4-O18	2.285(14)	Dy4-O23	2.336(14)
Dy4-O21	2.314(12)	Dy4-O333	2.382(13)	Dy4-O444	2.337(14)
Dy4-O114	2.401(13)	Dy4-O888	2.398(14)		

Table 3. Selected bond angles (°) for the Dy₄ aggregate

Bond angles (°)			
O3-Dy1-O1	74.0(5)	O1-Dy1-O5	145.2(5)
O3-Dy1-O5	88.6(5)	O3-Dy1-O7	77.0(5)
O1-Dy1-O7	79.4(5)	O5-Dy1-O7	67.3(5)
O11-Dy2-O9	71.7(5)	O11-Dy2-O6	92.6(5)
O9-Dy2-O6	132.2(5)	O15-Dy3-O13	68.1(5)
O15-Dy3-O17	105.7(6)	O13-Dy3-O17	139.2(5)
O18-Dy4-O21	144.8(5)	O18-Dy4-O23	94.8(5)
O21-Dy4-O23	73.7(5)	O18-Dy4-O19	69.3(5)
O21-Dy4-O19	75.7(5)	O23-Dy4-O19	76.9(5)
O111-Dy1-O444	70.3(5)	O111-Dy1-O114	69.8(5)
O111-Dy2-O444	70.7(4)	O111-Dy2-O333	73.8(5)
O111-Dy3-O333	72.9(5)	O111-Dy3-O114	69.5(4)
O114-Dy1-O444	71.3(5)	O114-Dy4-O444	71.2(5)
O114-Dy3-O333	69.0(4)	O114-Dy4-O333	67.8(5)
O333-Dy2-O444	67.9(4)	O333-Dy4-O444	67.2(5)

sample with the use of a Quantum Design SQUID magnetometer MPMS-XL. The dc measurements were collected from 1.8 to 300 K and from -70 to 70 kOe. Experimental data were also corrected for the sample holder and for the diamagnetic contribution calculated from Pascal constants²⁷.

Results and discussion

Crystal structure :

A single crystal X-ray study reveals that the compound (complex **1**) crystallizes in monoclinic space group P 1 21/c 1 with $a = 18.0965(11)$ Å, $b =$

$15.1210(4)$ Å, $c = 36.8631(17)$ Å, $\beta = 103.963(5)^\circ$, $V = 9789.06$ (82) Å³.

The asymmetric unit of tetra nuclear cubane structure consists of four Dy^{III} ions, six Schiff base ligands, five oxygen atoms, one chloride atom, four coordinated water molecules and seven uncoordinated water molecules (Fig. 1). Crystal packing diagram of Dy^{III} tetranuclear clusters of complex **1** is shown in Fig. 1b. Each Dy^{III} ion shows 8-fold coordination and ligated with carboxylate and phenalato groups of Schiff base ligands, μ_3 -OH groups, μ_2 -OH groups and water molecules. Earlier, Tang *et al.*, reported a

Fig. 1. (a) Atomic displacement at 50% probability of Dy^{III} cluster. (b) Crystal packing diagram of Dy^{III} tetranuclear clusters in complex **1**.

tetranuclear Dy^{III} complex with the same Schiff base ligand²⁸. In that cubane structure, four Schiff base ligands, two anthranilato moiety (resulting from hydrolysis of Schiff base) were involved in addition to four μ_3 -OH groups, two μ -OH groups and four water molecules. While using *N,N,N',N'*-tetrakis (2-hydroxy ethyl)ethylenediamine as a base in the synthesis of complex **1**, six Schiff base ligands in addition to four μ_3 -OH groups, two μ_2 -OH groups and four water molecules are involved in the construction of tetranuclear cluster. The coordination behaviour and lattice parameters of complex **1** are different from the previously reported structure.

The tetra nuclear cluster consists of four dissimilar Dy^{III} ions as shown in Fig. 2. Dy1 (Fig. 2a) is coordinated by two bidentate Schiff base ligands through the carboxylate oxygen atoms (O1, O5) and

the phenalato oxygen atoms (O3, O7), three μ_3 -OH groups (oxygen atoms O111, O444, O114) and a water molecule oxygen atom O666. Dy2 (Fig. 2c) is coordinated by one bidentate Schiff base ligand (carboxylate oxygen atom (O9) and phenalato oxygen atom (O11)), one carboxylate oxygen atom (O6) of another monodentate Schiff base ligand, three μ_3 -OH groups (oxygen atoms O111, O444, O333), one μ_2 -OH group (O555 oxygen atom) and a water molecule (oxygen atom O777). Dy3 (Fig. 2d) is coordinated by one bidentate Schiff base ligand (carboxylate oxygen atom (O13) and phenalato oxygen atom (O15)), one carboxylate oxygen atom (O17) of monodentate ligand, three μ_3 -OH⁻ groups (oxygen atoms O111, O444, O114), one μ_2 -OH⁻ group (O555 oxygen atom) and a water molecule (oxygen atom O999). Dy4 (Fig. 2e) is coordinated by two bidentate ligands (carboxylate oxygen atom (O18, O21) and phenalato oxygen atom (O19, O23)), three μ_3 -OH groups (oxygen atoms O333, O444, O114) and a water molecule (oxygen atom O888).

In this cubane structure, each Dy^{III} ion connected to other three metal centers via three μ_3 -OH bridges. Dy1 and Dy2 bridged through the μ -*O, O'*-carboxylate group of one LH⁻ ligand (oxygen atoms O5 and O6) and Dy3 and Dy4 bridged through the μ -*O, O'*-carboxylate group of another LH⁻ ligand (oxygen atoms O5 and O6). Dy2 and Dy3 connected through via one μ_2 -OH bridge. The Dy^{III}···Dy^{III} distances in tetranuclear cluster between 3.63 Å and 3.87 Å.

Thermal analysis :

Thermal stability of complex **1** was examined under N₂ atmosphere with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. As shown in Fig. 3, the weight loss of 5% at 100 °C corresponding to removal of uncoordinated water molecules. Second weight loss (4%) around 150 °C corresponds to removal of coordinated water molecules. The remaining weight loss up to 600 °C corresponds to the decomposition of organic ligand. Further heating beyond 600 °C leads to the decomposi-

Fig. 2. Coordination environment of the four dissimilar Dy^{III} ions in complex 1.

Fig. 3. TGA analysis of complex 1.

tion of crystal structure and dysprosium oxide will form. Formation of dysprosium oxide can be evident by the powder X-ray pattern.

Magnetic properties :

Direct-current (dc) magnetic susceptibility studies were carried out on complex 1, in the temperature range 300 K–2 K, with applied magnetic field of 1000 Oe. Fig. 3a shows the variation of $\chi_m T$ with T , where χ_m is the molar magnetic susceptibility. It was observed that $\chi_m T$ value is $55.4 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ at 300 K, which is lower than when compared with four uncoupled Dy^{III} ions. The gradual decrease in $\chi_m T$ value to a minimum value $27 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ K mol}^{-1}$ suggests depopulation of excited stark sublevels (Fig. 4).

Magnetization (M) data for complex 1 has been collected in the 0–40 KOe magnetic field range below 8 K temperature. Fig. 5 suggests that, the presence of significant anisotropy and low-lying excited states, as the curves of M vs H/T are of non-superposition in nature. It was also observed from the Fig. 3 that no

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of the $\chi_m T$ products at 1 kOe for complex **1**, normalizing all the data per Dy_4 unit.

Fig. 5. M versus H/T plots for complex **1** at different temperatures below 8 K, by normalizing the data per Dy_4 unit.

saturation magnetization for the sample between 8 K to 1.84 K. The decrease in magnetization than expected is due to the crystal field effect at the Dy^{III} ion that eliminates the 16-fold degeneracy of the ${}^6H_{15/2}$ at ground state.

To investigate the dynamics of the magnetization, alternative current (ac) susceptibility measurements were carried out for complex **1**. The occurrence of two distinct peaks (Fig. 6a and 6b) for out-of-phase ac signals is evident at higher frequencies and low frequency peaks (slow relaxation phase). Although

Fig. 6. Temperature dependence of the in-phase (a) and out-of-phase (b) ac susceptibility for complex **1** under zero dc field.

such ac signals are observed at 1.84 K, no hysteresis is noticed. The absence of hysteresis is may be due to presence of relatively fast zero-field relaxation.

Conclusions

In summary, a new tetranuclear Dy^{III} cubane cluster has been synthesized by using Schiff base ligand, 2-[(2-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-methylidene]amino} benzoic acid. Each Dy^{III} ion shows 8-fold coordination and exhibiting dodecahedral geometry. The cubane cluster shows dominant intra-complex ferromagnetic interactions and exhibiting magnetic anisotropy. Weak ac signals indicate that the dysprosium complex exhibiting SMM behaviour at temperature lower than 1.8 K.

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References

1. L. S. Guo, B. M. Day, Y. C. Chem, M.-L. Tang, A. Mansikkamaki and R. A. Layfield, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2017, **56**, 11445.
2. X.-Y. Wang, C. Avendano and K. R. Dunbar, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 3213.
3. J. Long, B. G. Shestakov, D. Lu, L. F. Chibotaru, Y. Guari, A. V. Cherkasov, G. K. Fukin, A. Trifonov and J. Larionova, *Chem. Commun.*, 2017, **53**, 4706.
4. R. Sessoli, D. Gatteschi, A. Caneschi and M. A. Novak, *Nature*, 1993, **365**, 141.
5. R. Sessoli, H. L. Tsai, A. R. Schake, S. Wang, J. B. Vincent, K. Folting, D. Gatteschi, G. Christou and D. N. Hendrickson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 1804.
6. G. Arom and E. Brechin, *Struct. Bonding (Berlin)*, 2006, **122**, 1.
7. C. J. Milios, A. Vinslava, W. Wernsdorfer, S. Moggach, S. Parsons, S. P. Perlepes, G. Christou and E. K. Brechin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 2754.
8. T. Lacelle, G. Brunet, A. Pialat, R. J. Holmberg, Y. Lan, B. Gabidullin, I. Korabkov, W. Wernsdorfer and M. Murugesu, *Dalton Trans.*, 2017, **46**, 2471.
9. L. G. Westin, M. Kritikos and A. Caneschi, *Chem. Commun.*, 2003, **8**, 1012.
10. G. Poneti, K. Bernot, L. Bogani, A. Caneschi, R. Sessoli, W. Wernsdorfer and D. Gatteschi, *Chem. Commun.*, 2007, **18**, 1807.
11. J. Tang, I. Hewitt, N. T. Madhu, G. Chastanet, W. Wernsdorfer, C. E. Anson, C. Benelli, R. Sessoli and A. K. Powell, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 1729.
12. X. J. Gu, R. Clrac, A. Hourri and D. F. Xue, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2008, **361**, 3873.
13. M. T. Gamer, Y. H. Lan, P. W. Roesky, A. K. Powell and R. Clrac, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **47**, 6581.
14. P. H. Lin, T. J. Burchell, R. Clrac and M. Murugesu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 8848.
15. Y. Z. Zheng, Y. H. Lan, C. E. Anson and A. K. Powell, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **47**, 10813.
16. K. Katoh, H. Isshiki, T. Komeda and M. C. Yamashita, *Chem. Rev.*, 2011, **255**, 2124.
17. N. Ishikawa, M. Sugita and W. Wernsdorfer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 3650.
18. D. N. Woodruff, R. E. P. Winpenny and R. A. Layfield, *Chem. Rev.*, 2013, **113**, 5110.
19. M. Murugesu, *Nature Chem.*, 2012, **4**, 347.
20. I. J. Hewitt, Y. H. Lan, C. E. Anson, J. Luzon, R. Sessoli and A. K. Powell, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, 6765.
21. Y. Gao, G.-F. Xu, L. Zhao, J. Tang and Z. Liu, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2009, **48**, 11495.
22. R. J. Blagg, C. A. Muryn, E. J. L. McInnes, F. Tuna and R. E. P. Winpenny, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 6530.
23. J. W. Sharples, Y.-Z. Zheng, F. Tuna, E. J. L. McInnes and D. Collison, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 7650.
24. H. Tian, M. Wang, L. Zhao, Y.-N. Guo, Y. Guo, J. Tang and Z. Liu, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2012, **18**, 442.
25. Y. H. Fan, C. F. Bi and J. Y. Li, *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, 2002, **254**, 641.
26. G. M. Sheldrick, SHELXS97, Program for the solution of crystal structures, University of Göttingen, Germany, 1997.
27. E. A. Boudreaux and L. N. Mulay (Eds.), "Theory and Applications of Molecular Paramagnetism", Wiley, New York, 1976.
28. H. Ke, P. Gamez, L. Zhao, G.-F. Xu, S. Xue and J. Tang, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **49**, 7549.

